

ISic4419

Epitaph for Aristarchos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 105 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Plinth (support for a stele) with moulding around the base. The plinth is heavily damaged and all the upper portion is lost and much of the lower moulding on the sides also; the lower part of the inscribed face is preserved, marked by a number of deep striations in the surface. The plinth is the left one of a pair mounted on a single base, classified as an epitymbion of type C.

Dimensions

Height 18.5 cm

Width 51.5 cm

Depth 52.5 cm

Layout

Remains of a single line of Greek letters, somewhat irregularly laid out and not following the horizontal

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregular plainly cut, widely spaced letters. Rho has closed and regular eye; sigma has horizontal upper and lower strokes, the intermediate strokes joined by a curve; alpha is broad with straight bar; omicron is small and mid-line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. [A]ρισταρχου

Apparatus

text based upon photographs

Sofia 2018: [A] ταρχ

Translation (en)

(tomb) of Aristarchos

Commentary

The majority of the epitaphs attested from this necropolis display a single name in the genitive. However, given the fragmentary state of this stone, it cannot be ruled out that this is the patronymic of the deceased, with a first name on the now lost upper portion of the stone. Against this, the second plinth from this funerary monument (ISic4420 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4420>]) clearly contains only a single name in the genitive, and it is therefore more likely that only the single name was also recorded here. The evidence of ISic4415 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4415>] / ISic4416 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4416>] and of ISic4417 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4417>] / ISic4418 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4418>] suggests that the two individuals commemorated by this stone and its pair ISic4420 were related (bothers?). The name Ἀρίσταρχος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BC%88%CF%81%CE%AF%CF%83%CF%84%CE%B1%CF%81%CF%87%CE%BF%CF%82] is widely attested, including c.11 attestations in Sicily (all from the eastern half of the island).

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4419>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4022733](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4022733)

Bibliography

Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon.

Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik. 206: 103-112. At 108 no.9 and fig.10

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4419. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381948>